

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: <i>not shot in</i> Max:	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1476 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	<i>Handwritten notes</i>
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In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #:	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION <i>construction cut for wall 1402</i>	Covered by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tiles) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)	Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: <i>1016</i>	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts: <i>1032, 1389</i>
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
dry sunny conditions, wall is still in situ, so SU has not been excavated

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: *eastern part of Area B 2011, runs N-S*
Shape: *linear*
NO OVERLAY

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:	Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations: <i>n.a. yes</i>	

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

INTERPRETATION

Construction cut for wall / lining 1402

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by **J FARR**

on **2.8.2011**

Revised by **CHM**

on **3.8.2011**

PDFd by **ELR**

on **3.8.11**

Entered by

on